

An open-source tool for modelling reservoir bottom gully head erosion volume

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Abstract— The study proposes a methodology for estimating the volume of gully head erosion using high-resolution datasets obtained through LiDAR technology and/or Structure from Motion (SfM), along with satellite images from Google Earth archives and orthophotos. Manual extraction of the boundaries of four active reservoir bottom gullies was performed across two different time periods. For 2012 – a high-resolution digital elevation model (0.25 m) derived from LiDAR data and Google Earth imagery were utilized; for 2019 – a high-resolution digital elevation model (0.25 m) derived from SfM data and orthophotos were employed. A Geographic Information System (GIS) methodology was developed that uses a single DEM to backcast or forecast topographic data for the computation of the gully head eroded volume between two time periods: 2012–2019 and 2019–2012 respectively. The reconstruction of the topography was achieved by interpolating the gully boundary and a series of simulated flow paths. As topography is known for both 2012 and 2019, the validation of the method could be performed.

The proposed methodology was implemented as a processing plugin within the Quantum GIS (QGIS) environment using the API for Python. This allowed for the development of a Processing Toolbox which includes two algorithms designed to backcast and forecast erosion processes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The estimation of geomorphological process rates has become an increasingly prominent research direction in geomorphology in recent years, largely due to the increasing accessibility of remote sensing data and techniques [1-5]. High-resolution topographic data acquired through LiDAR or Structure from Motion (SfM), combined with spatial information from aerial and satellite imagery, allow regional-scale analyses of process rates over the past two decades [6].

The lowland area of northeastern Romania, known as the Moldavian Plain (though more accurately a hilly landscape), has a long history of pond construction over the past 500 years. These reservoirs were typically small (under 1 million m³), shallow (4–5 meters deep, with water levels reaching up to 3 meters), and often dried up during summer or winter [7]. Built in response to the region's arid climate, they served as water storage, fish farming, and powering grain mills.

After their sedimentation, the dams were cut in the spillway area to facilitate underground water drainage, allowing the reservoir bottoms to be used as pastureland. This human intervention led to concentrated water flow in the spillway area during high discharge events, which facilitated the formation and evolution of gullies on the flat lacustrine deposits. Over 500 such gullies have been identified and mapped [7-8], some of which continue to evolve through headward retreat [6]. From the identified gullies, we selected four for which topographic data was available for both 2012 and 2019 to test the proposed methodology in this study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Figure 1. The methodology employed to backcast or forecast a DEM used for estimating the eroded volume of the gully heads

For each of the four gullies, boundaries from two different time periods were manually delineated using four different datasets: LiDAR DEMs and Google Earth imagery for the year 2012 and SfM DEMs and orthophotos for 2019. We have resorted to a manual delineation as the attempted automatic approaches on the DEM were not outlining the banks of the gully heads. As there is no straightforward approach to access historical imagery from Google Earth in QGIS, we have resorted to georeferencing them ourselves with the *Georeferencer* tool (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Workflow used in georeferencing the Google Earth imagery for 2012

The methodology makes use of a reference (t_0) high resolution DEM, to either forecast (t_1) or backcast (t_{-1}) another DEM. With our data, for forecasting, t_0 is the DEM for 2012 and t_1 the simulated DEM for 2019. For backcasting, t_0 is the DEM for 2019 and t_{-1} the simulated DEM for 2012. The simulated DEM is used

to estimate the eroded volume in the gully head areas. This is achieved by knowing the extent of the gully for either t_1 or t_{-1} from auxiliary data (Google Earth historical imagery, orthophotos). Validation is possible, as real DEM data is available for both 2012 and 2019, allowing the estimated eroded volumes for both t_{-1} and t_1 to be compared with the ground truth ones.

Figure 3. The simulated flow paths and ridge lines used in simulating a DEM

Figure 4. Example illustrating the simulated flow paths for forecasting, where t_0 is 2012. The skeleton and the real flow paths are merged to create multiple contiguous lines

The t_1 and t_{-1} DEMs are generated by estimating the elevation along simulated flow paths. For forecasting, the geometry of the flow paths for t_1 is simulated by merging the polygon centerlines generated based on the t_1 gully boundary with the flow paths from t_0 (Fig. 3, 4). The centerline was generated with the *v.voronoi.skeleton* GRASS GIS tool.

In the case of backcasting, the geometry of the flow paths for t_{-1} are assumed to coincide with the flow paths generated from t_0 (Fig. 3, 5) of which source points are located at the grid pixels

which overlap the t_0 gully limit. For t_1 , in addition to the simulated flow paths, the ridgelines from t_0 were also computed. The sampled elevation along the ridgelines of t_0 helps preserve the morphology of the terrain for and around the gully heads. After generating the flow paths and the ridge lines (Fig. 5), their geometries are intersected with the t_1 gully polygon.

Figure 5. Example illustrating the simulated flow paths and ridgelines in the backcasting case, where t_0 is 2019. The resulting geometries are intersected with the t_1 gully boundary and used for backcasting the t_1 DEM

The estimation of the topography along the simulated flow paths was based on the topography of the gully head at t_0 (Fig. 6). To extract the gully head at t_0 , a changepoint analysis was performed using the linearly penalized segmentation algorithm [9], implemented in the Ruptures Python library [10].

Figure 6. A theoretical example of generating the t_1 and t_{-1} heads using the topography of the t_0 head

Together with the sampled elevation along the boundary of the gully for either t_1 or t_{-1} , the generated set of points can be interpolated to obtain a simulated DEM. An interpolation method suited for scattered datasets is Multilevel B-Spline [11], which is implemented in the SAGA-GIS software [12]. After interpolation, a Gaussian filter was applied to smooth the final output.

III. RESULTS

We identified 27 active gully heads across the four analyzed gullies. For each, the eroded volumes between 2012–2019 were computed using both methods: backcasting and forecasting. After summing the eroded volumes of the heads in each gully, the estimations and associated errors are reported in Table 1. Errors are defined as the absolute difference between the ground truth and the estimated eroded volumes, expressed as a percentage of the ground truth volume.

Figure 7. Cross profiles for the forecasted 2019 DEM, comparing it with the ground truth

The forecasting approach proved to be robust, with errors ranging from 5.5% to 10.5% in estimated eroded gully head volume during the 2012–2019 interval, including two cases of overestimation and two of underestimation.

The backcasting approach produced significantly larger errors for two of the tested gullies, indicating that the methodology requires further refinement. Notably, all backcasting errors are cases of underestimation of eroded volume. These errors stem from the method's inability to accurately reconstruct the morphology of the gully head at t_{-1} , leading to underestimation of elevation (Fig. 8), and consequently, of eroded volume.

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

For the analyzed gullies, the forecasting approach yielded the best results, with errors up to 10%. However, the backcasting methodology needs further improvements. Some limitations are positional shifts between datasets and the subjectivity involved in delineating gully boundaries, especially those digitized from Google Earth imagery. The lack of higher quality imagery affected the proper delineation of the gully boundaries for t_{-1} . As the method assumes a simple relationship between a series of simulated gully channels and the gully boundary, complex topographic scenarios in the gully head fail to be simulated properly, which increases the errors.

Figure 8. Profile through the backcasted t_1 DEM for the gully with the highest error, comparing it with its ground truth

TABLE I. THE FORECASTED AND BACKCASTED ERODED VOLUMES AND THE ERRORS FOR EACH OF THE FOUR ANALYZED GULLIES

Latitude	47.7355 N	47.8937 N	47.7437 N	47.8765 N
Longitude	26.9390 E	26.8951 E	26.9243 E	26.8831 E
Eroded truth 2012-2019 (m³)	305.245	325.986	475.018	525.89
Estimated t_1 (m³)	337.131	345.569	449.073	474.834
Error t_1 (%)	10.446	6.007	5.462	9.708
Estimated t_1 (m³)	268.739	318.941	331.715	393.336
Error t_1 (%)	11.96	2.161	30.168	25.205

A QGIS processing toolbox plugin was developed to automate the process described and is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/alecsandrei/gully-erosion-modelling>). The plugin depends on the processing providers of GRASS GIS and SAGA GIS, as well as the Ruptures Python library which was used to perform the changepoint analysis. With this open-source approach we encourage reproducibility, suggestions and improvements from potential contributors. Upon further improvements, the plugin will also be available on the QGIS official plugin repository.

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